

A preliminary evaluation of a low cost UAV platform for vertical profiling of the atmospheric Temperature and Relative humidity.

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Abstract

The present study is a preliminary study in order to evaluate a low cost Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) performing vertical profiling of the atmospheric temperature and humidity, using additional sensor miniature data loggers. The performance of the UAV platform was tested multiple times during a hovering procedure and a vertical profiling procedure. The results ensure the ability of the UAV to perform vertical profiling successfully, and especially to capture several temperature and relative humidity inversions up to the maximum permitted height for license free UAV flights of 120m above ground.

Introduction

One of the common resources for vertical profiling of atmospheric temperature and humidity has been instrumented fixed towers, which can continually provide data at a point location over long periods of time. While highly reliable and configurable, instrumented towers do come with an inherent downside. Being limited in vertical extent, the convective boundary layer often extends well above even the tallest of towers.

The most popular solution for the last 100 years is balloon soundings that collect and deliver readings of different weather parameters. Unfortunately, these balloons are usually lost after deployment as they are carried away with the wind. Moreover, their landing spot is often not easily accessible; thus, they cannot be retrieved after descending. Highly sensitive and accurate measurement devices attached to the balloons increase the costs of their operational use. Therefore, balloon soundings are carried out only twice a day and only at selected locations. As a consequence, weather phenomena like fog, low stratus and storms cannot properly be predicted as they are triggered in the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL). One more disadvantage of balloon sounding is that they ascend too rapidly through the lowest levels.

A number of different attempts have been made to overcome this issue collecting more reliable data. Surface-based remote sensors such as wind profilers, Doppler lidars, sodars, and radiometers are capable of continuously observing a fixed location, but rely on numerous assumptions about the atmosphere and have trouble resolving

measurements close to the surface. These types of instruments are also cost-prohibitive when considering expansion to larger scale networks such as the global upper-air sites. Even when combining surface towers, balloons, and remote sensors with other observational techniques such as tethered balloons, Doppler weather radars, and satellite remote sensors, the US National Research Council [1] still concluded that the “vertical component of U.S. mesoscale observations is inadequate. Generally speaking, small unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) do not suffer from these issues. Therefore, they can improve the information gathered in the ABL by directly and accurately measuring prognostic variables. As UAVs are not lost during soundings, several atmospheric profiles can be flown in one session or even during a longer time period. Hence, a temporal evolution of the measured parameters can be observed.

Applications for atmospheric research have mostly been limited to the use of fixed-wing UAVs. The main disadvantages of using fixed-wing UAVs for wind velocity estimation is

1. The requirement to travel horizontally for some distance [2] making it impractical to measure vertical wind profiles or the temporal variability of the wind at one point in space
2. The risks when operating close to the ground
3. The need for a suitable surface for landing and possibly takeoff

In recent years, rotary-wing UAVs, also referred to as multirotor UAVs or copters, have been used widely for applications such as aerial imagery and their application in atmospheric research is increased in scientific literature last decade, especially since 2015. The advantages of the multirotor UAV than fixed wings UAV, include their vertical takeoff and landing capability and their ability to hover at a fixed point. These advantages make the multirotor UAV an ideal platform to measure vertical profiles or to obtain temporal changes of meteorological variables at a fixed location. Multirotor UAV are a potential replacement for balloon-based systems in the ABL, because they are low cost, easy to operate, durable in a wide range of atmospheric conditions, and reusable. Having such a reliable and repeatable method for atmospheric data collection will allow for detailed investigations of the structure and dynamics of the lower atmosphere (fog, low stratus and storms, temperature and flow field around areas and high buildings, sea vessels, etc.). Correspondingly, rapid growth in the developments of the autopilot capabilities, ground station software, and airframes is also being observed.

Universities and other academic institutes are developing multirotor UAV platforms for vertical profiles of meteorological variables. Most of them were based on rotary UAV platforms of the market (DJI S200, S600, S1000, phantom, 3DROBOTICS Iris+, etc) adding and testing devices on them, [8], [7], [6], [9] except the so called coptersond, built by the University of Oklahoma [1] [10] [11]. The major studies are briefed below:

University of Nebraska-Lincoln, used DJI Pro 600 Hexacopter platform, adding IMET-XQ sensors, in order to perform Temperature-humidity vertical profiling [7].

University of South Alabama used commercially available platform named Iris+ and quadcopter made by 3DRobotics, adding 10 IMET-XQ sensors, in order to perform Temperature-humidity vertical profiling [8].

University of Kentucky, used fixed wing Bluecat 5, solo UAV (made from 3d Robotics), DJI S1000, and DJI M600 UP platforms, adding IMET XQ T-H sensors, Trisonica & RM Young 81000 sonic anemometers, performing temperature, humidity and wind vertical profiles during a LAPSE-RATE team experiment [6].

Moscow State University, used markets DJI Phantom 4 UAVs, equipped with IMET XQ T-H sensors, together with Balloons, performing wind vertical profiles, based on approximations of the UAVs flight Log results [9].

Although the several above listed developed and tested UAV platforms, some major disadvantage are still remaining, such as the cost of the development of a special or market UAV platform, including the procedure and the cost of the additional sensor devices (temperature, relative humidity, etc) and the additional load of them (i.e. Imet XQ-sensors weight at about 140 gr), which could led to a sufficient reduction of the UAV battery consumption.

At the present study, an appropriate compact and low cost market multirotor UAV with additional low cost miniature and light T/RH sensors were used for successful vertical profiling of the T/RH atmospheric conditions, up to 120m above the ground. The hovering and vertical profiling procedures together with the ground based meteorological station and sensors were implemented in order to verify the capabilities of the UAV-sensor platform. Although this UAV platform may be developed further, it still can be a successful choice for the local weather forecast providers, technical companies and projects for flow simulation around buildings, people or societies that are interesting in weather phenomena, pollution protected authorities, chemical/petrochemical industries, Universities, etc. Another aspect of the present study is to describe step by step a simple general procedure to implement a market low cost UAV platform for vertical profiling.

Materials and methods

The UAV which is used for the present preliminary study is a quad copter TOYSKY S189 pro model (Fig. 1), with the characteristics defined in the table 1 below:

Toysky S189 pro TECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Max vertical ascend speed	1.6 m/s
Max vertical descend speed	1.0 m/s
Max speed (horizontal)	8m/s
Dimensions (length-height)	42 cm x 30 cm x 8,5 cm
Battery capacity	7.4V, 3.500mAh Li-Po
weight	468 gr
Main Rotor Diameter:	20 cm
Flight Time	25 min

Table 1: Technical characteristics of the UAV platform

The sensors which were used at the present study are listed in the table 2 below:

Sensor name	MANUFACTURER	TYPE-MODEL	Radiation shield	Manufacturer accuracy	Calibrated accuracy
Sen 1	Maxim Integrated ibutton	HYGROCHRONE DS 1923	Cylindrical (ABS plastic) R=3.24 cm H=5.24 cm	±0.5 °C	±0.185 °C
Sen 2	Maxim Integrated ibutton	HYGROCHRONE DS 1923	Cylindrical (ABS plastic) R=3.24 cm H=5.24 cm	±0.5 °C	±0.185 °C
Sen 3	Maxim Integrated ibutton	HYGROCHRONE DS 1923	Cylindrical (ABS plastic) R=3.24 cm H=5.24 cm	±0.5 °C	±0.185 °C
Sen 4	Maxim Integrated ibutton	HYGROCHRONE DS 1923	none	±0.5 °C	±0.185 °C
Reference weather station	DAVIS	VANTAGE PRO 2 aspirated (6153EU)	Cylindrical R=21 cm H= 21 cm	<u>Temperature:</u> SHT31/ ±0.3 °C(±0.2 °C from 10 °C to 40 °C) <u>Solar radiation intensity:</u> ±5% <u>Wind speed:</u> 0.9 m s ⁻¹ (resolution/sensitivity: 0.4 m s ⁻¹) <u>Relative humidity</u> ±3% (0 to 90% RH), ±4% (90 to 100% RH)	<u>Temperature:</u> SHT31/ ±0.05 °C from 10 °C to 40 °C)

Table 2: Sensor technical information

The Sensor sen 1 is situated on the ground, in an array of 1.80 m (Fig. 2), close to the reference ground-based weather station (Fig. 2,3). The sensor sen 2 was situated under the right front motor (30 mm from the center of the propeller-motor), within a radiation shield (Fig 1). The Sen 3 was situated under the left front motor, at a distance of 60 mm from the center of the propeller-motor, within a radiation shield. Sensor sen 4 was situated under the right rear motor, at a distance of 60 mm, without a radiation shield (Fig. 1).

Radiation shields were always used to protect the sensor from the solar heating [3]. The radiation shields of the present study (Fig. 1) are of cylindrical type and were constructed by ABS plastic.

Fig. 1 The UAV platform used at the resent study equipped with the miniature sensors and radiation shields

In order to achieve better radiation accuracy [12], the outer area of the shield is covered by aluminum foil and the inner by black insulating tape. The total weight of the radiation shield is almost 10 gr. Sensors were installed at a height of 1 cm from the bottom of the shield. Sensors were appropriately calibrated before the preliminary test procedure. Each one of the sensor weights 5 gr.

Figure 2: The test site where the hovering and vertical procedure were implemented

The Hovering procedure is a standard procedure that is used to verify the ability of the UAV sensors platform for accurate and representative measurements of the environmental conditions [10]. Immediately after the verification of the hovering procedure, the UAV platform is ready to perform the vertical profiling verification.

The hovering and the Vertical profiling procedures took place in an open space region (37°24' N, 22°43' E), next to a two-stage building (Fig. 2, 3).

The hovering procedure during the absence of the wind and solar radiation intensity may straightforwardly verify the appropriate position of the sensor module on the UAV platform (see lines 3, 5, 6, 8, table 3). The same procedure with the existence of the sufficient solar radiation intensity (lines 1, 2, 4, 7, table 3) and/or non-zero wind speed may verify the accuracy of the sensor/radiation shield owing to radiation error, one of the major errors occurring in meteorological observations.

Fig. 3: Closer photograph of the sen 1 ground based sensor and the UAV hovering at a fixed point

Results and discussion

Hovering procedure results

Hovering procedure took place in an open space region next to a two-stage building. During this procedure, the UAV was hovering in a fixed point at the front of the reference weather station (aspirated Davis Vantage pro 2) and the reference sensor (sen 1), as it is indicated in Fig. 2, 3. The sen 1 reference sensor is a same type of T/RH sensor, which was situated inside a same radiation shield (Fig. 3) as these used by the UAV (Fig. 1).

For the reason of non-disturbing the reference sensors due to the propeller-induced wind speed, the choice of a horizontal distance of 3 meters is adequate. The UAV remains almost stable during the procedure, even if the average wind speed/gusts were often moderate (dates 24/10/2023 & 14/10/2023)

Table 3 represents the temperature results of the sensor used during the hovering procedures, under several environmental conditions.

date	time	Duration (min)	Average Environmental conditions Davis Vantage pro 2 aspirated station (reference)					Sensor Average Temperature			
			Tem °C	Wind km/h	Wind Gust km/h	Solar w/m ²	RH %	Sen 1 °C	Sen 2 °C	Sen 3 °C	Sen 4 °C
			24/10/2023	14:06	11	26.6	1.5	1.75	640	54	29.17
24/10/2023	13:52	10	26.7	1.9	2.1	600	52	29.54	26.70	26.61	-
17/10/2023	18:47	17	21.3	0	0	15	75	22.3	21.34	21.23	-
15/10/2023	08:54	12	20.1	0	0	50*	66	23.1	20.10	20.05	22.84
15/10/2023	18:58	19	22.2	0	0	0	73	22.36	22.33	22.26	25.1
14/10/2023	18:43	17	22.8	0	0	12	63	23.1	22.9	22.8	25.11
14/10/2023	08:35	15	17.7	3	4.9	250	54	18.24	17.97	17.90	20.29
12/10/2023	18:00	7	24.6	0	0	5	34	26.1	24.78	24.77	-
AVERAGE			22.75					24.24	22.85	22.77	-
<i>*a cloudy morning</i>											

Table 3: temperature results of the sensor used during the hovering procedures, under several environmental conditions.

The general observations based on hovering procedure (Table 3) are listed below:

- The overall average temperature difference between the internal sensors sen 1, 2 is less than 0.08 °C. This means that the site of the sensor has adequate ventilation in order to ensure the accuracy of the results. The difference between them is minor and even lower than the accuracy of the sensors. Sensor temperature situated at the 3/5 of the propeller is lower than the sensor temperature situated next to the engine. Although this difference was expected to be higher [10], the reason could be the compact dimensions of the UAV.
- The use of an alternative solar radiation shield for the sensors is mandatory, in order to improve the accuracy of the temperature recordings by decreasing noticeably the effect of the solar radiation intensity. The absence of a shield could led to an increase of the temperature by almost 2-3 °C (this is the average differences between sen 2,3 and the unshielded sen 4).
- Shielded sensors situated under the propeller of the UAV have adequate ventilation and performed better than the same ground-shielded sensor without ventilation (average difference between sen 2, 3 and sen 1 was 1.4 C). Their behavior is closer to the reference weather station temperature sensor (Davis Vantage pro 2 aspirated).

Aspects which need further inspection, with a use of an UAV of improved flight characteristics (higher ascend/descend speed, higher battery capacity) and/or the use of a more accurate / lower response time T/RH sensor, are listed below:

- The choice of the exact cite of the sensor/shield on the UAV to minimize the temperature/humidity error
- The recognition of the heat and cold compartments of the UAV and their influence on the temperature-humidity values during the procedure
- The use of several shield dimensions in order to test the efficiency of the choice
- The influence of the solar zenith angle on the accuracy of the results

- The special calibration procedure of the sensors (number of points)

Vertical profiling results

During this preliminary evaluation, several vertical temperature and Relative Humidity profiles were captured, under different environmental conditions (Fig. 4 to 8).

Taking into account the relative low response time of the present sensors (<https://www.analog.com/media/en/technical-documentation/data-sheets/ds1923.pdf>), we keep the average ascend speed at a low value (less than 1 m/s). By this way, the response time error is reduced adequately [13, 15]. The sampling rate was chosen between 1 to 10 seconds. Owing to the limited battery capacity of the UAV, the results were captured only during the ascend procedure.

The height of the 120m is the maximum permitted height of an UAV, without license (flight plan approval) by the local authorities (Civil Aviation Service). The average time of the vertical procedure, including preparation (engine start, take-off and sensor stabilization), vertical stabilization, ascend, descend and landing, was almost 17 minutes on average.

General observations based on Fig. 4-8 are listed below:

- The present UAV with the ability of a Flight up to about 120 meter height captures well the vertical temperature and humidity profile of the environment.
- A 3rd order polynomial regression (Fig.6-8) as well as a B-spline approach (Fig. 4-5) are suitable to build the vertical profile of the Temperature and relative humidity.
- During stable atmosphere (Fig. 7-8), the slope of the temperature profile tends to coincide with the adiabatic temperature slope (0.6 °C/100m). During unstable conditions (Fig. 6), the slope is increased or reversed (Fig. 4-5)
- The vertical test procedure is able to capture a temperature/humidity inversion, especially when these were initially started at a height (i.e 40m, Fig. 4-5) from the ground.
- The present UAV operates normal during wind gusts of almost 8 km/h and even more (not tested at higher wind speeds)
- Vertical temperature / humidity differences ($\Delta T / \Delta H$), calculated from sen 2, 3 sensors differ by less than 0.23 °C/ 0.8% on average, during all vertical observations.
- Sensor sen 4 (the sensor without the radiation shield), captures higher temperature/humidity values than sen 2, 3 sensor, mostly owing to the higher radiation error and the absence of the radiation shield. Furthermore, a radiation shield may protect the sensor not only from the radiation heating but also from the induced side wind, which is often hotter in conduction with the heated parts of the UAV (battery and electronic compartment). A sensor without a shield is not appropriate for capturing the vertical profile of the Temperature/humidity
- The occurrence of the Humidity inversions is in relation with the temperature inversions as well (Fig. 4-5)

25/10/2023 TIME 08:47:00
 $T_{ave} = 19.3 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$
 $W_{ave} = 0 \text{ m/sec}$
Average Solar Radiation=140 w/m²
Average Rel. Humidity=82%
Average ascend speed=0.44 m/sec

Fig. 4: Temperature profiles (sen 2, 3, 4) and relative Humidity profiles during the vertical profiling of 25/10/2023. According to the UAV sensors, the starting point of the temperature inversion is situated between 25-40m

Fig. 5: Temperature profiles (sen 2, 3) and relative Humidity profiles during the vertical profiling of 24/10/2023. According to the UAV sensors, the starting point of the temperature inversion is situated at 45m. Temperature inversion thickness was almost 78-80m

Fig. 6: Temperature profiles (sen 2, 3) and relative Humidity profiles during the vertical profiling of 19/10/2023

Aspects which need further inspection, with a use of the present or an UAV of improved flight characteristics (higher ascend/descend speed, higher battery capacity) and/or more accurate / lower response time T/RH sensors, are listed below:

- The more accurate calculation of the height depending on the accurate temperature recordings
- The definition of a complete procedure of the smoothing of the vertical profile based on mathematical-statistical approach
- The need of multiple sensor response time calibrations, for an ambient air speed from 1 to 10 m/sec (standard procedure referred to 1 m/sec). Several tests show that the speed, immediately under the UAVs rotor (where sensors situated), exceed the value of 10 m/sec [14]. A need of a calibration of the sensor response time referred to an ambient speed of more than 5-10 m/s is mandatory in order to verify the robust reduction of the response time and thus the accuracy of the results.
- The calculation of the wind speed based on the UAV flight recorder file
- The comparizo between ascend and descend profiles
- The correction of the response time error of the sensor and the selection of the most suitable sampling rate
- The maximum wind gusts where a selected UAV may work appropriately

The vertical profile of T/RH above the maximum permitted height of 120m The ability of capturing inversions above 120m

- Further investigation of the differences in $\Delta T/\Delta H$ between the selected sensor-shield/ sites

According to the results above, the preliminary evaluation of the procedure of the design of an UAV ensures most of the steps of the procedure described in the present proposal. Especially, the ability of capturing the inversions is the most serious aspect of the preliminary approach, because Temperature inversion is an important contributor to cloud formation, visibility, pollution, etc.:. Here is how temperature inversions affect our environment:

- **Visibility:** Cooler air gets trapped within a layer of warmer air, and the moisture condenses and forms clouds called smog. But since these clouds cannot escape the level of inversion, they cause poor visibility in that region.
- **Rainfall:** Because the clouds cannot get high enough, there is no rain. This has adverse effects on the agriculture industry.
- **Diurnal variations:** Temperature inversion also affects the usual fluctuations in temperature throughout the day. Typically, the sun's radiation heats the ground during the day. The heat energy transfers to the air above the ground through convection and conduction. Due to the accumulation of cool air in temperature-inverted areas, the heat transfer is minimal, and diurnal temperature variation is slight.

- **Thunderstorms and tornados:** Inversions also cause intense thunderstorms and tornadoes because of the energy trapped high up in the atmosphere.
- **Pollution:** Finally, smoke, dust, and pollutant particles get trapped in the lower part of troposphere, and they can react with each other to form chemicals that are hazardous when inhaled, like smog.

Fig.7: Temperature profiles (sen 2, 3) during the vertical procedure of 18/10/2023

Fig.8: Temperature profiles (sen 2, 3) during the vertical procedure of 16/10/2023

Conclusions

The results ensure the ability of the UAV to perform vertical profiling successfully, and especially to capture several temperature and relative humidity inversions, up to the maximum permitted height of 120m above ground.

An appropriate designed radiation shield is mandatory for the on-board sensor of the UAV platform. Shield is protecting not only from solar radiation heating but even from side induced hot stream in contact with the electronic and battery compartment of the UAV.

The effective-designed radiation shields (2 items) including the sensors, weight almost 30 gr. In case where only one sensor is needed, the additional weight to the UAV platform is about 15gr. These loads are the lowest that could be added in a UAV for performing vertical profiling of T/RH since now, giving the ability to use them to the most of the low cost UAV platforms without sufficient pay load and with almost zero additional battery consumption.

A sensor/shield under the rotor has adequate ventilation in order to produce accurate and representative results of the temperature and relative humidity. However, owing to compact dimensions of the UAV, the exact appropriate position is not completely obvious.

A low ascend speed is appropriate for the reduction of the response time of the sensors.

The present UAV operates normal during wind gusts of almost 8 km/h and even more.

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